

STRENGTH OF COMPOSITE LAMINATE WITH MULTIPLE HOLES

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SUMMARY

An experimental study was conducted to determine the effects of hole pattern arrangements on the strength of structural composite laminates. The results reveal that the strength of the laminates is the highest with two in-line holes (a top and bottom array) and the lowest with four holes in a diamond array pattern. This data can lead to better understanding the effects of various damage scenarios and the corresponding repair design needed to restore a laminate's structural integrity.

Keywords: composite laminate; multiple holes; laminate strength; composite repair

INTRODUCTION

In structural assemblies, joining two composite structural parts by fastening has been one of the most commonly used methods in manufacturing and repairing of composite structures. In addition, holes in the structure are often used for providing access to areas for damage inspection or installation of electrical and piping systems. In repairs, multiple holes in different patterns or arrays result when mechanically joining the patch laminate to parent laminates with moderate thicknesses.

The presence of holes in a structure results in a high stress gradient at the vicinity of their edges. The strength prediction of isotropic material with a hole can be accurately predicted since the stress gradient around the hole is not dependent of the material. However, unlike isotropic material, the stress gradient around a hole in laminated composites is not only dependent on material constants, but also fiber orientation and laminate stacking sequence. This complex stress gradient results in a complicated failure mechanism near the hole. Hence, the prediction of the laminated composite with a hole is usually based upon empirical methods. To do so, a series of tests are conducted to establish the strength predictive curves. Those curves are only applicable for the particular material system and the laminate stacking sequence of the given test coupons. Moreover, the presence of other holes near the given hole often occurs in composite design practice and this array of holes in different patterns may also affect the strength of laminate.

Previous Research

The study of a hole in laminated composites has been extensively documented. A thorough review of theoretical and experimental studies on laminates with a single hole was given by Awerbuch and Madhukar [1] and Tan [2]. Few works have concentrated on multiple holes in laminated composites.

Fan and Wu [3] employed the Faber series expansion to obtain the stress concentration factor for an infinite sized laminate with multiple holes. Hansaw, Sorem and Glaessgen [4] conducted ply-by-ply analysis using finite elements to obtain equivalent stress concentrations for infinitely sized composite laminates with multiple holes under tensile and shear loading. Comparisons of the stress distribution around the holes for infinitely sized laminates with three holes were given.

In other studies of using the finite element method, Ochoa and Reddy [5] determined the stress concentration factor in composite laminates having three holes placed in-line with a tensile load. Neelkanthan, Shah and Chan [6] obtained the stress distribution around multiple circular loaded holes in a stiffener reinforced laminate. Later, Vendhagiri and Chan [7] investigated the stress distribution around the hole in composite bonded and bolted joints. Esp [8], using the least square boundary collocation method for anisotropic composite laminates, investigated the strength of composite laminate with two unloaded holes placed in close proximity. Recently, Kheradiya [9] studied the effect of the stress concentration on a finite width laminate with multiple holes.

The effect of the interaction of differently arranged multiple holes on a laminate's strength have not been extensively studied before. Thus, the main objective of this study is to investigate the effect of variously arranged hole arrays on the strength and failure modes of laminated composites. The understanding of the interaction effect that occurs may provide a guideline in designing fastened repairs in laminated composites.

Failure Mechanism of laminate with hole

The failure mechanism of the laminates with a hole depends on whether the laminates are thin or thick. In a thin laminate, longitudinal splitting and angle ply splitting at the edge of the hole often occur first. Then, delamination failure occurs at the region between the two splittings. Finally, fiber breakage occurs at the net section of the laminate. For thick laminates, the splitting and delamination failure modes seldom appear significant. Instead, fiber breakage dominates. A detailed description of the failure process of laminates with hole is contained in reference 10.

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

Description of Test Coupons and Test Procedures

Five configurations of hole orientation patterns, figure 1, in a graphite/epoxy laminate with a lay up of $[\pm 45/0_3/90]_s$ were studied. Configuration A contains a single hole, designated as SH. Configurations B and C have two holes, with one having in-line

holes (top and bottom), designated TBH, and one having side-by-side holes, designated SSH. Four holes placed in a square (SA) and diamond (DA) arrays are configurations D and E respectively. The coupons were manufactured by The Boeing Company.

Figure 1 Hole Configurations Evaluated in Composite Coupons

The holes are all $\frac{1}{4}$ -inch in diameter and the distance between holes in both the side by side and top and bottom hole configurations is 0.75 inches. Aluminium end tabs, 2-inches long, were attached with film adhesive and an axial strain gage was bonded to the specimen at the location away from the hole. The coupons were inspected to see if any damage occurred around the hole during fabrication. A white marking, using Liquid Paper ink, was painted along the edges of specimen and at the vicinity of the holes to enhance visibility of any damage when present.

The specimens were loaded to failure at a rate of 0.02 inch per minute using an MTS test frame. The load and strain data were automatically recorded through a data acquisition system. The test was interrupted and pictures were taken when the damage was observed.

Test Results and Damage Observations

The resulting strengths of each laminate with various configurations are shown in Figure 2. The test data scatter from the three to five samples are also shown. The data indicates that configuration B has the highest strength, whereas configuration E, having the four holes in a diamond array, has the lowest strength.

All of the test specimens exhibited an edge delamination before the presence of the visible damage around the hole. Figure 3a shows this edge delamination along one of the specimens. The final failure occurs in the neighborhood of the hole for all of the specimens except for configuration A, the specimen with a single hole. For the single hole specimen, multiple failures are observed not only in the neighborhood of the hole but also at locations away from the hole. For this specimen, failure away from the hole can be attributed to the effect of edge delamination.

Figure 2 Test Results

A comparison of the failure modes for configurations A and B is shown in Figure 3b. For specimen with the top/bottom holes, significant failure was observed along the longitudinal direction (see figure 3b). This is indicative of a ply splitting failure occurring at the 0^0 plies.

a) Edge delamination

Single Hole
ult = 155.760 ksi

Top & Bottom Hole
ult = 165.987 ksi

b) single and top/bottom holes

Figure 3 Failure comparisons of laminates with various configurations

Figure 4a shows the failure comparison of configurations C and D specimens. Significant fiber breakage is observed between the two side-by-side holes in configuration C. Because of fiber breakage between holes, the strength of configuration C is lower than configuration D. For the four-hole specimens, figure 4b, extensive

fiber breakages are shown in configuration E resulting in the lowest strength among all of the configurations.

Figure 4 Failure comparisons of laminates with various configurations

ANALYTICAL STUDY

The finite element method (FEM) was used to investigate the effect of stress concentrations around the periphery of a hole in the laminate configurations shown in Figure 1. A three-dimensional model of ANSYS 10.0 classic was used for this study.

Development of the FEM Model

Meshing

The SOLID186 high-order element of ANSYS was used. Because of the high stress gradient around the hole, a 20-node high order element with quadratic shape function was chosen to achieve a higher accuracy in the results. Each of the layers in the laminate is meshed with a separate hexahedron element along the thickness direction. Element sizes have been selected to maintain proper aspect ratio of less than 20 for all elements generated.

The size of the model is chosen as 5 inches long and 1.5 inches wide. Because of symmetry in the thickness direction, only half of laminate is modeled. Since the 45° and -45° layers are not symmetric with respect to the x- and y- directions, the advantage of modeling a quarter laminate can not be used. Instead, a full in-plane model is adopted in this model.

Boundary and Loading Conditions

The translation degree of freedom in the z-axis is constrained for all nodes at $z=0$. All of the nodes at one end face are constrained along the longitudinal direction. All of the nodes along the vertical center line on the x-constrained face are constrained along the y-direction.

An in-plane nominal tensile stress of 100 psi is applied to all the cases considered. The stress is applied to the end face along the longitudinal direction on which the boundary conditions are not applied.

Convergence and Model Validation

A convergence study was conducted for the laminate with a single hole only. The number of elements around the hole periphery are used in the convergence study. The maximum magnitude of stress at the hole periphery is used for comparison. A total of 96 elements along the hole periphery is elected for the entire study.

The model was validated by comparing the stress concentration factor for an isotropic material. For a finite width isotropic plate subjected to tensile loading, the stress concentration factor given in Reference 11 was used for comparison. The result of the stress concentration factor for the model is obtained within 2% of the value shown in Reference 9.

Analytical Results

Normalized Maximum stress

The maximum stress in each ply occurs at the place where the direction of the fibers is tangential to the edge of the hole. This indication will be explained later in the “FEM Result” section. The maximum value of the stresses in each ply is normalized by the applied stress. The results are listed in Table 1.

As indicated, normalized σ_1 is dominant in the 0^0 ply for all of the laminates. It is interesting to note that σ_1 in configurations B and D are lower than that of configurations A and C, respectively. This implies that the presence of another hole along the loading direction in a laminate with a hole would result in reducing the maximum stress. This can be explained in that the stress distribution around the hole is smoothed out along the loading direction.

The data from configuration C shows that the normalized σ_1 is much higher than that of configuration A. This is due to reduction of the net section of the laminate. For normalized σ_2 and τ_{12} , the higher values occur at 45^0 ply.

The data also indicates that the configuration E laminate exhibits the highest normalized stress components among the laminates tested. If the final failure of the laminate is governed by the maximum stress governed by 0^0 ply, it implies that configuration E has the lowest strength among all of the configurations. This indication is confirmed from the test results.

Table 1 Maximum stress of each ply in various configurations.

Fiber Orientation for Ply	Normalized Maximum stress, σ_1 (psi)				
	A	B	C	D	E
90.0	1.077	1.075	1.079	1.068	1.077
-45.0	1.808	1.789	2.008	2.044	2.353
45.0	2.057	2.009	2.249	2.262	2.685
0.0	6.904	6.502	7.680	7.550	10.380

Fiber Orientation for Ply	Normalized Maximum stress, σ_2 (psi)				
	A	B	C	D	E
90.0	0.559	0.555	0.563	0.485	0.953
-45.0	1.505	1.529	1.733	1.684	1.971
45.0	1.594	1.567	1.771	1.661	2.038
0.0	0.317	0.314	0.349	0.356	0.462

Fiber Orientation for Ply	Normalized Maximum stress τ_{12} (psi)				
	A	B	C	D	E
90.0	0.205	0.204	0.229	0.263	0.430
-45.0	0.509	0.453	0.612	0.570	1.064
45.0	2.060	2.003	2.243	2.214	2.675
0.0	0.563	0.551	0.630	0.734	0.838

Stress Contours

Figure 4a shows the imaginary force lines around the hole when the laminate is subjected to an axial load. The concentration of force lines indicates the occurrence of the higher stress. With the presence of a hole along the loading direction, the force lines will be redistributed resulting in less line concentration at the edge of the hole. Because of the load carried by the fibers, the higher stress occurs at the edge of the hole where the fibers are tangential to it as illustrated in figure 4b. Because of the highest stress values occur at the 0^0 ply, only the stress contours for σ_1 is shown in figure 5.

a) Imaginary force lines of 0^0 plies

b) Fibers tangential to the edge of the hole

Figure 4 Stress Contours

Figure 5 Stress contour of σ_1 in 0° ply of all the configurations

The dark shaded area along the loading direction indicates zero to negligible stress. The maximum value occurs at the tangential point on the edge of the hole. As indicated, the presence of another hole along the loading direction results in the elongation of the dark shaded area. This implies that the force lines are redistributed in a more uniform manner across the laminate. In the side-by-side holes (two holes and four holes), the maximum stress occurs at the place close to the edge of the laminate. However, for the four holes in the diamond array pattern, the maximum stress is at the inner edge.

CONCLUSION

An experimental and analytical study was conducted to investigate the effects of hole patterns on the strength of a typical structural laminate. The test results indicate that the strength of the laminates with a single hole is lower than that of the laminate with two holes placed in a top and bottom array and higher than that of a laminate with two holes in a side-by-side array. Comparing laminates with holes placed in the side-by-side array, the strength of the four-hole laminate with a square array is higher than the two-hole side-by-side array. The lowest strength laminate is for four-hole laminate arranged in a diamond array.

The analysis results reveal that the maximum stress along the fiber direction in the 0° ply is reduced when another hole is placed along the loading direction. The highest maximum stress value occurs in the four-hole laminate arranged in a diamond array. It is concluded that the array of multiple holes should be placed along the loading direction in design practice.

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